

Continuum modelling of direct seawater electrolysis for green hydrogen production: Quantifying the effects of hypochlorite/hypochlorous acid equilibrium and mass transport limitations

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Abstract

This study presents an open-source continuum modelling framework for direct seawater electrolysis (DSWE) based on an anion exchange membrane water electrolyser architecture. The model couples laminar flow, tertiary current distribution, Nernst-Planck ion transport, Butler-Volmer electrode kinetics, and pH-dependent chlorine-oxychlorine equilibrium chemistry. Particular emphasis is placed on resolving the competition between the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) and chlorine evolution reaction (CER), which remains one of the central barriers to selective and durable seawater electrolysis. The framework explicitly accounts for local hydroxide transport, chloride oxidation, hypochlorous acid formation, hypochlorite speciation, and membrane-mediated ion transport. Model behaviour is evaluated against experimentally reported polarisation trends for NiFe-(CO₃²⁻)-LDH-3 and IG@Ni-NiMoO_x based seawater electrolysis systems. The results reproduce the qualitative transition from chlorine-dominated behaviour at low current densities toward increasingly oxygen-selective operation at higher current densities. The model therefore provides a transparent mechanistic basis for analysing transport-driven OER/CER selectivity in DSWE and supports future optimisation and techno-economic assessment of AEM-based seawater electrolysis systems.

Keywords

Direct seawater electrolysis, Green hydrogen production, Continuum modelling, Tertiary current distribution, Nernst-Planck transport, Oxygen evolution reaction, Chlorine evolution reaction, Hypochlorous acid equilibrium, Mass transport limitations, Open-source modelling

1 Background

DSWE has emerged as a promising pathway for sustainable hydrogen production because it potentially eliminates the energy-intensive desalination and purification stages required in conventional freshwater electrolysis systems [1, 2]. Hydrogen itself is increasingly recognised as an important clean energy carrier due to its relatively high specific energy of approximately 120–142 MJ kg⁻¹ [3] and its potential for near-zero-emission production through renewable-powered water electrolysis [4].

Conventional electrolysis technologies, however, generally require highly purified freshwater feeds. Proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers (PEMWEs), for example, typically require ultrapure water with conductivities below approximately 1 μS cm⁻¹, total dissolved solids below approximately 1 ppm, and resistivities approaching 18.2 MΩ cm to avoid membrane degradation, catalyst contamination, and conductivity losses [5]. This presents a major sustainability challenge because freshwater constitutes only approximately 3% of global water resources, whereas nearly 97% exists as seawater [6]. In addition, green hydrogen production pathways generally exhibit significantly higher levelised costs of hydrogen (LCOH) relative to conventional grey hydrogen production routes, which remain among the cheapest hydrogen production methods due to established infrastructure and lower feedstock costs [7]. Consequently, DSWE presents an attractive alternative because it directly utilises abundant seawater resources while potentially avoiding costly desalination and purification stages, thereby offering a possible pathway toward reducing both freshwater dependence and upstream treatment costs in large-scale hydrogen production systems.

Despite these advantages, DSWE faces major electrochemical challenges associated with the competition between the desired OER versus the undesired CER at the anode. In chloride-rich seawater environments containing approximately 0.5 M chloride ions [8], the equilibrium potentials of OER and CER differ by only approximately 130 mV [8, 9]. Consequently, relatively small variations in local pH, ionic transport, membrane behaviour, and

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overpotential can significantly alter anodic selectivity, in favour of chlorine evolution. Furthermore, chlorine evolution produces reactive chlorine species such as Cl_2 , HOCl , and OCl^- , which contribute to local acidification, membrane degradation, catalyst degradation, and reduced oxygen selectivity [9].

Among existing electrolysis architectures, anion exchange membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE) has emerged as one of the most promising platforms for DSWE because it combines alkaline operation with membrane-separated electrode compartments. Alkaline operation favours OER relative to CER and additionally permits the use of earth-abundant transition-metal catalysts such as NiFe-, NiMo-, and Co-based materials [10]. Consequently, many recent DSWE studies employ AEM-based architectures together with selective OER catalysts and engineered membrane/electrolyte configurations to minimise chlorine formation. In membrane-separated systems, anion exchange membranes may additionally experience chloride crossover, swelling, and reduced permselectivity under chloride-rich conditions [11, 12]. These coupled reaction–transport interactions therefore make DSWE substantially more complex than conventional freshwater electrolysis systems.

Despite growing interest in DSWE, major modelling gaps remain. Many existing continuum models simplify chlorine chemistry by considering only the Cl_2/Cl^- system while neglecting extended chlorine–oxychlorine equilibria involving species such as HOCl and OCl^- . In addition, many available studies rely heavily on proprietary commercial finite-element software platforms, limiting transparency and reproducibility.

This work addresses these gaps by developing an open-source continuum model for membrane-separated DSWE systems based on an AEMWE architecture. The framework couples laminar flow hydrodynamics, tertiary current distribution, multicomponent Nernst–Planck ion transport, Butler–Volmer electrochemical kinetics, membrane-mediated hydroxide transport, and pH-dependent chlorine–oxychlorine equilibrium chemistry within a unified Python-based modelling environment. Particular emphasis is placed on resolving transport-driven OER/CER selectivity behaviour and the role of chlorine-speciation equilibria in governing local anodic electrochemical environments.

More broadly, the framework also contributes toward establishing the mechanistic foundations required for future techno-economic assessment (TEA) of AEM-based seawater electrolysis systems. Detailed mechanistic descriptions of membrane transport, hydroxide migration, chlorine speciation, and local pH evolution are important for generating the physics-based performance data required for more reliable future TEA studies of emerging DSWE technologies [13].

2 Configuration and Geometry

The computational domain employed in this study represents a two-dimensional membrane-separated DSWE cell based on an AEMWE architecture. The model consists of three primary contiguous regions, namely the anodic flow channel (Region A), the anion exchange membrane (Region B), and the cathodic flow channel (Region C), as illustrated in Figure 1. The geometry was constructed to resolve coupled ionic transport, electrochemical reactions, and fluid flow within the anodic and cathodic compartments while explicitly accounting for the membrane region and electrochemically active catalyst interfaces (boundaries 1 and 10).

The anodic compartment has a width of 5 mm and contains the NiFe–(CO_3^{2-})–LDH-3 electrocatalyst, where both the OER and CER occur. The cathodic compartment, also 5 mm wide, contains the IG@Ni–NiMoO_x catalyst, where the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) takes place. The selection of these electrode materials follows the experimentally validated seawater electrolysis configuration reported by Deng et al. [14]. Separating the two electrolyte compartments is a centrally positioned Fumasep FAA-3–50 anion exchange membrane with an effective hydrated thickness of 0.05 mm. The total cell width is therefore 10.05 mm, while the total cell height is 50 mm.

Electron transport is assumed to occur externally through current collectors and external circuit, whereas hydroxide ion transport occurs internally through the membrane from the cathode toward the anode. The catalyst layers are represented as interfaces rather than explicitly resolved volumetric regions.

Figure 1: Two-dimensional computational geometry of the membrane-separated DSWE system based on an AEMWE architecture. Region A represents the anodic flow channel, Region B denotes the anion exchange membrane, and Region C corresponds to the cathodic flow channel. Boundaries 2 and 8 correspond to the anodic and cathodic outlet boundaries, respectively, while boundaries 3 and 9 represent the corresponding electrolyte inlet boundaries. Boundaries 4 and 7 denote the electrochemically active catalyst interfaces where the anodic OER/CER and cathodic HER reactions occur. Electron transport occurs externally through the current collectors and bipolar plates, while hydroxide ions migrate internally through the membrane from the cathode toward the anode. The schematic is not drawn to scale.

The model is formulated under steady-state, isothermal, single-phase conditions. Seawater is treated as a Newtonian, incompressible electrolyte with constant physical properties. Laminar flow is imposed in the anodic and cathodic channels, while the membrane is treated as an idealised anion-selective region that permits only hydroxide transport. This treatment of the AEM represents a deliberate simplification in the present work, as detailed membrane phenomena such as chloride crossover, membrane swelling, water transport, variable permselectivity, and

membrane degradation are not explicitly resolved. A more comprehensive membrane treatment will be incorporated in future extended models. Gas bubble formation, bubble-induced resistance, and thermal gradients are additionally neglected in the present version of the framework.

Electrolyte flow is described using the incompressible continuity and Navier–Stokes equations [15]:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the electrolyte velocity vector.

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}. \quad (2)$$

Here, ρ is the electrolyte density, \mathbf{u} is the electrolyte velocity vector, p is pressure, and μ is the dynamic viscosity of the electrolyte.

Ionic transport is represented using a tertiary current distribution framework based on the Nernst–Planck formulation [16]:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla c_i = R_i, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{J}_i is the ionic flux of species i , \mathbf{u} is the electrolyte velocity vector, c_i is the concentration of species i , and R_i is the volumetric production or consumption rate of species i .

The ionic flux is expressed as

$$\mathbf{J}_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - z_i u_i F c_i \nabla \phi_l. \quad (4)$$

Here, D_i is the diffusion coefficient of species i , z_i is the ionic charge number, u_i is the ionic mobility, F is Faraday’s constant, c_i is the species concentration, and ϕ_l is the electrolyte-phase potential.

The ionic mobility is related to diffusivity through the Nernst–Einstein relation [17]:

$$u_i = \frac{D_i}{RT}. \quad (5)$$

Here, u_i is the ionic mobility, D_i is the diffusion coefficient, R is the universal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature.

Bulk electroneutrality is imposed throughout the electrolyte domain:

$$\sum_i z_i c_i = 0. \quad (6)$$

Here, z_i is the ionic charge number of species i , and c_i is the concentration of species i .

Electrode kinetics are described using concentration-dependent Butler–Volmer equations [18]:

$$i_j = i_{j,\text{ref}} \left[g_{a,j} \exp\left(\alpha_{a,j} \frac{F\eta_j}{RT}\right) - g_{c,j} \exp\left(-\alpha_{c,j} \frac{F\eta_j}{RT}\right) \right], \quad (7)$$

where i_j is the local current density for reaction j , $i_{j,\text{ref}}$ is the reference exchange current density, $g_{a,j}$ and $g_{c,j}$ are concentration-dependent anodic and cathodic activity terms, $\alpha_{a,j}$ and $\alpha_{c,j}$ are the anodic and cathodic charge-transfer coefficients, F is Faraday’s constant, η_j is the overpotential, R is the universal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature.

The overpotential is defined as

$$\eta_j = \phi_s - \phi_l - E_{\text{eq},j}. \quad (8)$$

Here, η_j is the reaction overpotential, ϕ_s is the solid-phase potential, ϕ_l is the electrolyte-phase potential, and $E_{\text{eq},j}$ is the equilibrium potential of reaction j .

The OER is represented through the reversible equilibrium [18]:

with equilibrium potential

$$E_{\text{eq}}^{\text{OER}} = 1.229 - 0.059 \text{ pH}. \quad (10)$$

Here, $E_{\text{eq}}^{\text{OER}}$ is the equilibrium potential for the OER, and pH is the local electrolyte pH.

The chlorine evolution pathway is resolved using pH-dependent chlorine–oxychlorine equilibria [8, 9, 19]. Under acidic conditions:

while near-neutral and alkaline conditions are represented (respectively) through

and

The homogeneous chlorine-speciation equilibria are additionally resolved through

and

At the cathode, the HER is represented by [20]

The membrane is treated as an ideal hydroxide-conducting AEM [21, 22], where the hydroxide flux is expressed as

$$\mathbf{J}_{\text{OH}^-,m} = -D_{\text{OH}^-,m} \nabla c_{\text{OH}^-} + u_{\text{OH}^-,m} F c_{\text{OH}^-} \nabla \phi_l. \quad (17)$$

Here, $\mathbf{J}_{\text{OH}^-,m}$ is the hydroxide flux through the membrane, $D_{\text{OH}^-,m}$ is the effective hydroxide diffusion coefficient in the membrane, c_{OH^-} is the hydroxide concentration, $u_{\text{OH}^-,m}$ is the hydroxide ionic mobility in the membrane, F is Faraday’s constant, and ϕ_l is the electrolyte-phase potential.

Faradaic selectivity toward oxygen evolution is evaluated according to

$$\text{FE}_{\text{OER}} = \frac{i_{\text{OER}}}{i_{\text{OER}} + \sum i_{\text{CER}}} \times 100\%. \quad (18)$$

Here, FE_{OER} is the Faradaic efficiency toward oxygen evolution, i_{OER} is the oxygen evolution current density, and $\sum i_{\text{CER}}$ represents the total chlorine evolution current density contributions.

Together, these equations couple laminar hydrodynamics, multicomponent ion transport, membrane-mediated hydroxide migration, Butler–Volmer electrochemical kinetics, and pH-dependent chlorine speciation within a unified continuum framework for membrane-separated DSWE.

3 Results and Discussion

The model was evaluated against experimentally reported DSWE behaviour for NiFe–(CO₃²⁻)–LDH-3 anodic catalyst coupled with IG@Ni–NiMoO_x cathodic catalyst [14]. Figure 2 compares the simulated polarisation behaviour with the experimentally observed trend. The comparison focuses primarily on the transition between chlorine-dominated and oxygen-selective anodic operation under increasing current density.

The model successfully reproduces the experimentally observed transition from chlorine-dominated behaviour at relatively low current densities toward increasingly oxygen-selective operation at higher anodic current densities. At low current density, the local anodic environment remains insufficiently alkaline to strongly suppress the chlorine evolution reaction CER. Under these conditions, chloride oxidation remains thermodynamically and kinetically competitive with the OER, resulting in relatively high chlorine selectivity [1, 8]. Furthermore, the limited OH⁻ flux transported through the membrane under low-current operation

restricts the development of alkaline conditions near the anodic interface.

As current density increases, enhanced hydroxide transport from the cathode toward the anode progressively elevates the local anodic pH. This increase in alkalinity promotes OER activity while simultaneously shifting the chlorine equilibrium toward hypochlorite formation through the HOCl/OCl^- equilibrium pathway [19]. Consequently, oxygen selectivity improves progressively above approximately $200\text{--}300\text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, consistent with experimentally reported observations for alkaline DSWE systems employing selective OER catalysts [9, 14]. The simulated transition therefore demonstrates that membrane-mediated OH^- transport plays a central role in regulating anodic selectivity.

The results further demonstrate that OER/CER competition in DSWE is not governed solely by intrinsic electrode kinetics, but rather by the coupled interaction between local pH, ionic transport, membrane selectivity, electrolyte composition, and chlorine–oxychlorine speciation. In particular, the model predicts that local acidification resulting from chlorine hydrolysis can reinforce CER activity under transport-limited conditions. This behaviour agrees qualitatively with previous studies reporting strong coupling between chlorine chemistry and local electrochemical microenvironments in seawater electrolysis systems [8, 9].

In addition, the results highlight the importance of explicitly resolving chlorine-speciation equilibria within continuum DSWE models. Many existing models simplify the chlorine pathway to only the Cl_2/Cl^- redox pair, thereby neglecting the important role of HOCl and OCl^- in governing local pH and anodic selectivity. The present framework demonstrates that these equilibria substantially influence the spatial distribution of reactive chlorine species and therefore affect predicted OER/CER competition. The inclusion of coupled chlorine–oxychlorine chemistry consequently improves the mechanistic fidelity of the model.

The validation plot therefore supports the use of the present continuum framework as a mechanistic tool for interpreting anodic selectivity trends in membrane-separated DSWE systems. More broadly, the model establishes a physically transparent platform for studying the interactions between membrane transport, local pH gradients, chlorine chemistry, and electrochemical kinetics in alkaline seawater electrolysis architectures.

4 Model Limitations

Although the model correctly reproduces the principal qualitative trends in anodic selectivity and chlorine-speciation behaviour, several limitations remain. Firstly, gas bubble dynamics and multiphase transport effects are neglected. In practical DSWE systems, the evolution of O_2 , H_2 , and Cl_2 bubbles can significantly modify local hydrodynamics, electrolyte conductivity, active surface area, and mass-transfer behaviour [10]. Bubble accumulation near the electrode surface may also increase local ohmic resistance and alter effective reaction kinetics, especially at high current densities.

Secondly, thermal transport effects are neglected through the assumption of isothermal operation. In reality, Joule heating and reaction-induced temperature gradients may alter electrolyte conductivity, diffusion coefficients, membrane hydration behaviour, and equilibrium potentials during operation [23, 24]. These thermal effects may become increasingly important under industrially relevant current densities.

Figure 2: Comparison between simulated and experimentally reported selectivity behaviour for direct seawater electrolysis systems employing $\text{NiFe}-(\text{CO}_3^{2-})\text{-LDH-3}$ anodic catalysts [14]. The model reproduces the experimentally observed transition from chlorine-dominated operation at low current densities toward increasingly oxygen-selective operation at higher current densities.

Thirdly, the membrane is represented using an idealised anion-selective transport approximation in which only OH^- transport is permitted. Actual AEMs may exhibit partial crossover of chloride, hypochlorite, dissolved chlorine species, and water molecules, leading to membrane swelling, reduced permselectivity, and long-term degradation [11, 12]. Consequently, the present membrane treatment likely underestimates the complexity of practical membrane transport behaviour in chloride-rich environments.

Furthermore, homogeneous chlorine chemistry is represented using equilibrium relationships rather than fully resolved transient reaction kinetics. Although this assumption remains reasonable under near-equilibrium conditions, transient local reaction pathways and intermediate oxychlorine species may become important during highly dynamic operation or under strong concentration gradients.

Finally, the present validation remains qualitative and limited primarily to experimentally reported selectivity trends and polarisation behaviour. Additional validation against spatially resolved pH measurements, chlorine concentration distributions, membrane crossover data, and local current-density mapping would further strengthen the predictive capability of the framework.

Future work will therefore focus on extending the model to include multiphase gas evolution, experimentally calibrated membrane transport parameters, non-isothermal effects, transient chlorine chemistry, and more comprehensive experimental validation. The integration of these features will improve predictive accuracy and facilitate the development of more realistic techno-economic assessments of AEM-based DSWE systems.

5 Conclusions

This work presented an open-source continuum modelling framework for DSWE based on an AEMWE architecture. The framework couples laminar flow hydrodynamics, tertiary current distribution, multicomponent Nernst–Planck ion transport, Butler–Volmer electrochemical kinetics, membrane-mediated hydroxide

transport, and pH-dependent chlorine–oxychlorine equilibrium chemistry within a unified continuum modelling environment. By explicitly resolving the coupled interaction between ionic transport, membrane behaviour, local pH evolution, and chlorine chemistry, the model provides a mechanistically detailed representation of anodic selectivity behaviour in membrane-separated DSWE systems.

The results successfully reproduce the experimentally observed transition from chlorine-dominated anodic behaviour at relatively low current densities toward increasingly oxygen-selective operation at higher anodic current densities. The model demonstrates that anodic selectivity in DSWE is not governed solely by intrinsic electrode kinetics, but rather by the strong coupling between hydroxide transport, electrolyte composition, membrane selectivity, local pH gradients, and chlorine-speciation equilibria. In particular, the results highlight the critical role of membrane-mediated OH^- transport in promoting anodic alkalinity and suppressing chlorine evolution under high-current operation.

The framework further demonstrates the importance of explicitly resolving chlorine–oxychlorine equilibrium pathways when modelling seawater electrolysis systems. The inclusion of coupled Cl_2 , HOCl , and OCl^- equilibria significantly improves the mechanistic fidelity of the model and enables more realistic prediction of transport-driven OER/CER competition. The results therefore establish a direct mechanistic relationship between membrane transport limitations, local electrochemical microenvironments, chlorine chemistry, and anodic selectivity in alkaline seawater electrolysis architectures.

More broadly, the present work contributes toward the development of transparent and reproducible open-source electrochemical modelling methodologies for seawater electrolysis systems. Unlike many existing DSWE studies that rely heavily on proprietary commercial software platforms, the present framework provides an open, physically interpretable and extensible modelling approach suitable for future integration with advanced membrane models, multiphase transport formulations, experimental validation studies, and techno-economic assessment frameworks.

Although several simplifications remain, including the neglect of gas-evolution dynamics, thermal transport effects, transient homogeneous reaction kinetics, and detailed membrane crossover phenomena, the framework nevertheless provides a strong foundation for analysing coupled reaction–transport interactions in membrane-separated DSWE systems. Future work will therefore focus on extending the model to include experimentally calibrated membrane transport parameters, multiphase gas evolution, non-isothermal operation, and spatially resolved validation against experimental pH and concentration measurements.

Overall, the framework establishes a mechanistic basis for understanding transport-driven anodic selectivity in DSWE and provides a useful platform for future optimisation and scale-up studies aimed at the development of selective, durable, and economically viable seawater electrolysis technologies for sustainable hydrogen production.

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